

Equilibrium Studies on the Formation of Mixed-Ligand Complexes in Solution. Part III†

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Equilibrium studies on the formation of the ternary complex MAB [where M = copper(II), nickel(II) or zinc(II) ion, A = aspartate and B = glycinate, α -alaninate, β -alaninate, ethylenediamine or malonate ion] have been carried out in aqueous solution using pH-metric technique. The overall formation constants of the complexes have been evaluated at 30° and ionic strength of 0.2M(NaNO₃). The stability constants are found to follow the Irving-Williams order. The values of the constants are correlated and discussed in terms of basicity of the donor sites, size of the metal chelate ring, charge neutralization and statistical considerations. The distributions of different complex species present in the solution as a function of pH is illustrated for a representative system.

MIXED-LIGAND complexes of metal ions have been extensively studied in recent years following the recognition that these play an important role in biological processes¹⁻³. The ternary complexes have been implicated in the storage and transport of active substances through membranes. Many of the analytical methods based on complex formation involve the formation of mixed chelates⁴. The formation of such complexes are statistically more favoured and frequently they are of favoured stability also⁵. Mixed-ligand complexes formed by biologically active ligands like amino acids and polypeptides can serve as model systems for the study of the more complicated phenomena occurring in biological systems. Ternary complexes of various metal ions involving amino acids, diamines and carboxylic acids have been extensively studied⁶⁻⁸. There have been some reports of complexes of metal ions with aspartic acid as the primary ligand and a few amino acids as secondary ligands⁹⁻¹¹. Studies on the formation of mixed-ligand complexes by Cu(II), Ni(II) and Zn(II) with DL-aspartic acid as the primary ligand and glycine, DL- α -alanine, β -alanine, L-serine, ethylenediamine (en) and malonic acid as secondary ligands are reported in this paper.

Experimental

All the amino acids and malonic acid used were of A. R. grade and were used as such. Ethylenediamine (L. R. grade) was dried over potassium hydroxide pellets, distilled and the fraction boiling at 117° was collected. All solutions were prepared from double distilled water. Metal salt solutions were prepared from their respective A. R. nitrates and standardised using standard procedures¹². Solutions of ethylenediamine and malonic acid were standardised potentiometrically.

The titrations were carried out under an atmosphere of nitrogen in a thermostated bath at 30 ± 0.1° and an ionic strength of 0.2 M(NaNO₃). A digital pH meter (ECIL, pH 822A, accuracy ± 0.01 pH unit) was used to measure the pH. The instrument was calibrated before each titration using standard buffer solutions. The pH value was converted into hydrogen ion concentration using a hydrogen ion activity coefficient¹³ of 0.8.

Computation : The equilibria involved in ternary complex formation was solved by the approach of simultaneous formation of ternary complex. A computation procedure similar to that of Martin and Paris¹⁴ was developed.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants of the ligands used were redetermined under the present experimental conditions by the method of Albert and Serjeant¹⁵. The Calvin and Wilson titration technique¹⁶ was adopted for the study of the formation of binary complexes. The method of Irving and Rossotti¹⁷ was applied for the evaluation of the stability constants. The values of the ionisation constants and the stability constants of the binary complexes, given in Table 1, are in good agreement with the literature values¹⁸.

The variation of pH with the number of moles of base added (per mole of metal ion) for Ni(II)-aspartic acid-secondary ligand system is shown in Fig. 1. Curve 1 represents the Ni(II)-aspartic acid titration in 1 : 1 molar ratio and curve 2 the Ni(II)-aspartic acid-glycine titration in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio. The buffer region of complex formation in the second curve is lowered relative to curve 1 indicating that glycine is simultaneously involved in coordination to the metal ion along with aspartic

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TABLE 1—IONISATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY COMPLEXES
 $t=30\pm 0.1^\circ$; $\mu=0.2M$ (NaNO₃)

Sl. No.	Ligand	pK_1	pK_2	pK_3
1.	DL-Aspartic acid	—	3.76 ± 0.02	9.50 ± 0.02
2.	Glycine	2.33 ± 0.01	9.53 ± 0.03	—
3.	DL- α -Alanine	2.35 ± 0.01	9.61 ± 0.04	—
4.	β -Alanine	3.60 ± 0.01	10.16 ± 0.04	—
5.	L-Serine	2.25 ± 0.01	8.95 ± 0.02	—
6.	en	7.12 ± 0.02	9.82 ± 0.04	—
7.	Malonic acid	2.68 ± 0.02	5.22 ± 0.02	—

Sl. No.	Ligand		Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Zn(II)
1.	DL-Aspartic acid	log K_1	8.83 ± 0.05	7.16 ± 0.04	5.79 ± 0.06
		log K_2	6.89 ± 0.08	5.20 ± 0.05	4.26 ± 0.05
2.	Glycine	log K_1	8.19 ± 0.03	5.83 ± 0.04	5.02 ± 0.03
		log K_2	6.85 ± 0.04	4.81 ± 0.03	4.20 ± 0.05
3.	DL- α -Alanine	log K_1	8.12 ± 0.04	5.51 ± 0.05	4.81 ± 0.04
		log K_2	6.71 ± 0.05	4.47 ± 0.03	4.02 ± 0.05
4.	β -Alanine	log K_1	7.04 ± 0.02	4.64 ± 0.03	—
		log K_2	5.54 ± 0.06	3.33 ± 0.05	—
5.	L-Serine	log K_1	7.84 ± 0.02	5.40 ± 0.03	4.68 ± 0.04
		log K_2	6.47 ± 0.06	4.28 ± 0.04	3.71 ± 0.05
6.	en	log K_1	10.52 ± 0.07	7.40 ± 0.05	5.92 ± 0.06
		log K_2	9.13 ± 0.06	6.31 ± 0.05	4.90 ± 0.05
7.	Malonic acid	log K_1	4.97 ± 0.04	3.17 ± 0.05	2.69 ± 0.03
		log K_2	2.78 ± 0.06	—	—

Fig. 1. Ni(II)-aspartic acid-secondary ligand system: pH -metric titrations
 1. $Ni(NO_3)_2(0.003 M)$ + aspartic acid (0.003 M)
 2. $Ni(NO_3)_2(0.003 M)$ + aspartic acid (0.003 M) + glycine (0.003 M)
 3. $Ni(NO_3)_2(0.003 M)$ + aspartic acid (0.003 M) + β -alanine (0.003 M)
 4. $Ni(NO_3)_2(0.003 M)$ + aspartic acid (0.003 M) + $HNO_3(0.006 M)$ + en (0.003 M)
 5. $Ni(NO_3)_2(0.003 M)$ + aspartic acid (0.003 M) + malonic acid (0.003 M)

acid. The lowering of buffer region of complex formation in the case of en and malonic acid is much greater compared to glycine curve revealing that ternary complex formation commences at relatively lower pH values in these cases. The formation constant of the ternary complex and the concentration of the various species present in the solution were made in pH region 5 to 7 in the case of Cu(II) and 5.5 to 8 and 5.5 to 7.5 in the cases of Ni(II) and Zn(II) respectively. Following the observation of earlier workers^{9,10} only one ternary complex was presumed to be present in these pH ranges under the concentrations of the metal ion and ligands employed. The values of the stability constants of the mixed-ligand complexes evaluated in the present study are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 2—M(II)-ASPARTATE-LIGAND(B) SYSTEM: STABILITY CONSTANTS* OF TERNARY COMPLEXES
 $t=30\pm 0.1^\circ$; $\mu=0.2M$ (NaNO₃)

Sl. No.	Ligand(B)		Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Zn(II)
1.	Glycinate	log β_{MAB}	15.62	11.94	10.08
			(15.78) ⁺	(11.89) ⁺	—
		log K_{MAB}	6.80	4.78	4.29
2.	DL- α -Alaninate	$\Delta \log K$	-1.39	-1.04	-0.78
		log β_{MAB}	15.50	11.48	9.78
		log K_{MAB}	6.68	4.32	3.94
3.	β -Alaninate	$\Delta \log K$	-1.44	-1.19	-0.89
		log β_{MAB}	14.78	10.84	—
		log K_{MAB}	5.96	3.68	—
4.	L-Serinate	$\Delta \log K$	-1.08	-0.96	—
		log β_{MAB}	15.30	11.46	9.68
		log K_{MAB}	6.48	4.30	3.89
5.	en	$\Delta \log K$	-1.36	-1.10	-0.79
		log β_{MAB}	18.33	13.72	11.11
		log K_{MAB}	9.51	6.56	5.32
6.	Malonate	$\Delta \log K$	-1.01	-0.84	-0.60
		log β_{MAB}	12.10	9.22	7.80
		log K_{MAB}	3.28	2.06	2.01
		$\Delta \log K$	-1.69	-1.11	-0.68

* The general accuracy of the results is ± 0.1 log unit.
⁺ Literature values from references 9 and 10.

It can be seen from Table 2 that for all the systems investigated the β_{MAB} values follow the Irving-Williams order, Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II)¹¹. The β_{MAB} values of the β -alaninate complexes are less than the corresponding values of the α -amino acid complexes due to the less favoured six-membered ring formed by β -alanine compared to the five-membered ring formed by α -amino acids. Despite the comparable basicities of the amino groups, the stability values for the α -alanine system are less than those for the glycinate complexes possibly due to the steric effects caused by the methyl group in α -alanine. The lower formation constants of the serinate complexes relative to the glycinate complexes are not surprising since the basicity of the amino group in serine is less than

that in glycine. The β_{MAB} values for M(II)-aspartic acid-en are higher than those of other systems investigated since this mixed chelate, of all systems studied, contains the optimum number of nitrogen and oxygen atoms as donors and the stability of the mixed chelates involving malonate is the least due to the presence of only one nitrogen atom as donor.

The extent to which the ternary complexes are favoured can be inferred from the value of $\Delta \log K$, the difference between the stability constants, $(\log K_{MAB} - \log K_{MB})$, where K_{MAB} is the equilibrium constant for the reaction $MA + B \rightleftharpoons MAB$ and K_{MB} the equilibrium constant for $M + B \rightleftharpoons MB$. Sigel²⁰ has shown that when both the primary and secondary ligands are bidentate, the statistical value of $\Delta \log K$ is -0.4 for octahedral complexes. Similar calculations indicate that when one of the ligands is terdentate, the statistical value of $\Delta \log K$ is -0.7 . An experimental value of $\Delta \log K$ close to or greater than the statistical value indicates favoured formation of the ternary complex. According to Sigel²⁰ the statistical value of $\Delta \log K$ for metal ions like Cu(II) forming distorted octahedral complexes will be lower. The $\Delta \log K$ values in Table 2 indicate that in the case of Ni(II) and Zn(II) the values are closer to the statistical value indicating favoured formation of ternary chelates. The $\Delta \log K$ values for Cu(II) are less than those for nickel(II) and zinc(II) possibly due to the distorted octahedral coordination.

The $\Delta \log K$ values in Table 2 indicate that the ternary complex involving en is more favoured compared to other secondary ligands for all the metal ions investigated. This is due to the effect of charge neutralisation which is one of the significant factors that favour the formation of mixed-ligand complexes. The formation of neutral ternary chelate from the parent complexes can be represented as below :

With amino acid or malonic acid as secondary ligand, only charged ternary complexes are formed. The favoured formation of mixed-ligand complexes as a result of charge neutralisation has been observed by many workers²¹.

The favoured formation of ternary complexes can also be illustrated by a study of the distribution of various complex species present in the solution as a percentage of total metal ion concentration and their variation with pH. Representative species distribution curves for the Ni(II)-aspartate- α -alaninate system are shown in Fig. 2. The uncomplexed metal ion is present to the extent of 40% of the total metal ion concentration at pH 5.6 and [Ni(aspartate)] species to the extent of 55% at the same pH. The concentration of [Ni(aspartate)] reaches a maximum of 70% at pH 6.4 and then gradually decreases with increase in pH.

Fig. 2. Ni(II)-aspartate(A)- α -alaninate(B) system. Distribution of complex species as a function of pH

1. Ni, 2. NiA, 3. NiA₂, 4. NiB, 5. NiB₂, and 6. NiAB

[Ni(aspartate)₂] and [Ni(alaninate)] complexes are formed in appreciable amounts around pH 6 and their concentrations increase as the pH is raised. The percentage of [Ni(alaninate)₂] species, less than 5 at pH 7, increases to 10 at pH 8. The ternary chelate [Ni(aspartate)(alaninate)] is formed in significant concentration above pH 6.6. Its concentration increases with pH and is around 25% at pH 8.

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